

Kerala Rural Navigation with Google Maps: User Insight and Challenges

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Abstract - This study examines the efficiency of Google map for navigation in rural areas and it is mainly focusing on Kerala. And the study also highlights user's needs and the challenges they faced because of using this navigation system. While comparing urban areas with rural areas, urban areas have well-established navigation solutions and some distinct navigational complexities are present in rural areas. Through comprehensive surveys and feedback from the users, this research seeks to ascertain the efficiency of Google Maps in meeting the navigation needs of rural users without any complexities. By understanding user experiences and point out specific challenges, this study aims to provide actionable insights for the enhancement of navigation tools to rural areas, this will ultimately help to improve navigation efficiency and usability in these areas.

Keywords: Google Map; Rural areas; Navigation; Location; Routing

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital world, location-based services like Google Map have transformed how we use technology and offering personalized experiences based on our location. Study on this topic also explores user perceptions, preferences, and satisfaction to this feature in this digital environment. Navigation in rural areas presents completely unique challenges as compared urban environments mainly due to limited infrastructure, sparse population density and diverse terrain. While urban navigation the Google Maps have provided correct direction to specific location without any complexities and it also notifies the user if there any troubles are present in their way. By understanding the utility of navigation tools in rural areas it performs a very significant role in improving accessibility and usability for residents, travellers, and businesses operations in these regions. This study mainly focuses into the effectiveness of Google Maps [12] for navigation in rural areas

and also on user perspectives and identifying challenges associated with it.

Rural areas often lack detailed mapping data, accurate information about the way to reach the destination, and lacking of real-time traffic updates, and also making navigation more challenging. And travelling through the way they provided may reach at a location and it may be far apart from our destination. By this small reason we will affect our precious time and money spent for this travel. Additionally, the unique characteristics of rural landscapes, are unpaved roads, agricultural fields, and remote landmarks, and because of these characteristics we need a specialized navigation features in the location-based services.

Through comprehensive surveys and user feedback, this research aims to evaluate the usability of Google Maps in meeting the navigation needs of users in the rural regions. The findings of this research paper endeavour to contribute the action through which we improving navigation efficiency and usability in rural areas, also facilitates smoother travelling experiences.

II. GOOGLE MAP SERVICES

a. Use of location -based Services

In this digital world, location-based services, are provided by apps like Google Maps [3] have become essential tools and they also have a significant role in the impact our daily routines. When comparing the current situation with the past the Google Maps, for instance, goes beyond traditional navigation by allowing users to explore and find nearby businesses, read reviews from users, and share their own recommendations and the situation they faced in their life. It's not just about getting from point A to B and it is all about making informed decisions based on our surroundings.

And the widespread adoption of location-based services like Google Maps reflects a broader trend between people in the society, where

people increasingly rely on location-based services to enhance convenience, connectivity and all also to make the journey stress free. Whether checking real-time traffic updates, to find the nearest hotel, or to share the latest hotspot with friends, all these services play a crucial role in shaping how we navigate and experience the world around us. So, these location-based services make our digital interactions more personalized and also efficient.

b. About Google Map

Google Maps is a fantastic tool that makes the access to the location details in just a finger-tip [1]. For example, if you're exploring a new city or just trying to find the nearest coffee shop or a particular institution, Google Maps will help you to locate within a limit period of time. And it can be used in your phone or computer to see maps, find places of interest, and also provides the step-by-step directions. It even helps you from the troubles like traffic jams and also suggests the fastest routes. Additional feature they provided is you can read reviews from other people to discover the best spots near you and by checking out real photography of places. It will make your journey a bit more enjoyable without any confusion related to location you are looking for travel.

The key feature of Google Maps that makes it cooler is its ability to show you a street view of locations. And through a few clicks, you can virtually explore streets and neighbourhoods, helping you get a feel for a place before you even set foot there. It's not just a map – it's your virtual guide to the world, it helps the people it easily discovers new places and plan your adventures with confidence. And it is very less time consuming in this busy world.

c. Getting Started with Google Maps on Your Phone

We can use Google Maps very easily on our smartphone for finding and exploring and new places within a few clicks. A step-by-step guide on how to use Google Maps on smartphones is given below [3]:

- Open Google Maps: Open the Google Maps app icon on your home screen or find it in your app drawer in the smartphone.
- Search for a Location: And then type the location you want to find at the search bar.
- Share Your Location: Make sure that the location is on your smartphone and then back to the app and Tap on the blue

dot that shows your current location to access more options. You can also share your location with friends or also helps to get more details about the surroundings.

- Get Directions: Once the location is identified, then tap on it. You will see details about the location. And to find out the directions, tap "Directions," and then choose your starting point. Google Maps will definitely provide a turn-by-turn directions.
- Explore Nearby Places: To discover nearby places like restaurants or any other institutions, tap the "Explore" tab at the bottom. This shows you the most popular categories and places nearby to it.

d. Advantages of using Google Maps

Some advantages [2] they are listed below:

- Navigation Assistance: Google Maps provides turn-by-turn navigation, and also guides the users to their destination efficiently and helping them avoid traffic troubles.
- Real-Time Traffic Updates: Users can access real-time traffic information, thereby enabling them to choose the fastest route to reach the destination without lost the precious time and also avoid congested areas.
- Location Sharing: The platform allows users to share their current location with friends and family, it will definitely help you to coordinate meetings easily.
- Explore Nearby Places: Users can discover nearby places of interest, by using the "Explore" feature in the Google Map.
- Offline Maps: Google Maps allows users to download maps for offline use, and this feature is very useful when navigating in areas with limited or no internet connectivity.
- Street View: The "Street View" feature provides a virtual tour of streets and neighbourhoods, and this helping the users to familiarize themselves with a location before visiting and this give an overview about the place. And after that the user will able to take a correct decision about their travel.
- Voice Navigation: Users can receive turn-by-turn directions through voice prompts, and it is very helpful feature while driving.

5. Disadvantages of using Google Maps

While Google Maps is a widely used and valuable navigation tool, it does have some disadvantages [2] they are listed below:

- **Privacy Concerns:** Google Maps tracks the location data, raising privacy concerns regarding the collection and use of personal information.
- **Data Usage:** And more mobile data is required if we continuous use Google Maps for a long period of time.
- **Battery Consumption:** The app can be a drain on your device's battery, especially during the extreme usage for navigation or location tracking.
- **Reliance on Internet Connection:** Google Maps heavily relies on a stable internet connection and in some rural and urban areas the internet connection very bad in that situation the app may not function effectively.
- **Mapping Errors:** Sometimes the Maps may also contain inaccuracies, outdated information, or errors, and this will make the user into a potential confusion and inconvenience in the travel.
- **Limited Offline Functionality:** While Google Maps offers offline maps, this feature has limitations like real-time traffic updates, may not be provided.
- **Security Risks:** Sometimes our real-time location-based information may fall into wrong hands and this will make security risks and all.
- **Limited Indoor Navigation:** Google Maps is primarily designed for outdoor navigation, and its indoor mapping capabilities are limited, so it less effective in malls or airports.

III. LITERATURE SURVEY

a. Google Maps

In this review of the literature, Heeket Mehta's paper "Google Maps"[4] is the main topic. The document offers a thorough explanation of Google Maps' features and operation. Google Maps, which was first created in C++ by Lars and Jens Eilstrup Rasmussen, is now a sophisticated navigation program that includes features like street view and estimated time of arrival (ETA). The paper explores the fundamental algorithms used by Google Maps to determine the shortest path between two points, such as Dijkstra's algorithm and the more effective A* algorithm. In addition to this it also clarifies the workings of location tracking through GPS and also

highlights the concepts of trilateration and triangulation.

b. The Importance of Google Maps for Traffic in Calculating the Level of Service for the Road and Traffic Delay

Urban traffic congestion is a critical issue that is made a bad condition by increase in the population and also an increase in the use of private vehicles, these causes major delays and costs. This is mainly highlighted in the paper "The Importance of Google Maps for Traffic in Calculating the Level of Service for the Road and Traffic Delay"[5] by K S Ali and N M Abid. It promotes the usage of online tools such as Google traffic maps to collect the data quickly on traffic conditions throughout the world in real time.

Worldwide, urban regions are facing a lot of serious problems with traffic congestion due to a number of variables, that includes population growth, economic development, and need for transportation facilities. The Conventional techniques used for estimating traffic jams and delays are really expensive and time-consuming. On the other hand, when we consider the new technologies—like Google traffic maps— it provides an economical and practical way to collect traffic data in real time.

Traffic congestion is caused by a number of reasons, such as road construction, driver behaviour, traffic light stops, and accidents. Even though Google Maps provides insightful information on the state of the traffic, it might not always foresee unforeseen variables that worsen traffic. All things considered, Google traffic maps are essential for evaluating traffic jams and delays since they give academics and decision-makers useful information for properly addressing urban transportation issues.

c. Google Maps Security Concerns

Aqil Burney, Muhammad Asif, and Zain Abbas' paper "Google Maps Security Concerns"[6] examines the profound effects of Google Maps and other Geographic Information System (GIS) maps on a range of contemporary activities, such as travel, business planning, agriculture, marketing, and urban planning. Although Google Maps transforms location-based search and navigation, there are security problems associated with its extensive use. This study draws attention to the fact that possible dangers of utilizing Google Maps, including the possibility that its anonymous characteristics and lack of a specific logging history could be mainly used for criminal purposes like terrorism, espionage, and kidnapping. And for successfully

reduce potential threats, it highlights the importance of addressing these security issues and makes suggestions by which the Google Maps should be improved.

Google Maps has transformed navigation and is now a necessary tool for everyday life, it helps a lot for organizing business trips, vacations, and to conduct other tasks. But because the site has lacked security controls and permits anonymous access, there are notified security problems associated with its wide use. There is also a possibility for the misuse of people with bad intentions, such as terrorists and criminals. The study mainly divides Google Maps users into two groups: Anonymous Good Users and Anonymous Bad Users. The first group consists of law-abiding persons who use the service in an innocent and correct manner, while the second group creates security dangers by using the platform for the objectives, such as scheming to organize criminal operations or obtaining liable information. The report recommends a number of actions to address these security risks, such as putting in place a sign-up mechanism to gather user credentials, keeping track of user activity using session logs, and using history logs to anticipate and spot unusual conduct. These protective measures seek to reduce the dangers connected to cyberterrorism and other illegal activities.

d. Image Localization Using Google Maps

The usage of image localization and registration techniques, specifically for point out specific images within a larger-regions, using Google Maps is covered in the paper "Image Localization Using Google Maps"[7] written by Sadashiv D. Lavange, A. D. Vishwakarma, H. T. Ingale, and V. D. Chaudhari. The main aim of the project is to create an algorithm that can accurately locate template images—like rooftop areas—inside of expansive aerial photos that may be downloaded from Google Earth.

Researchers can precisely understand the area of solar rooftops and provide support for green energy programs by using Google Earth pictures. Obtaining Google Earth photos using latitude and longitude coordinates and registering template images into these images are among the issues the study notified. MATLAB technology is used to perform 2-D cross-correlation and it is mainly used for picture registration and to access Google Earth services. The study recommends a technique for converting colour prints to grayscale and highlights the value of grayscale images for processing. To count, the research offers insightful information about how to apply

image localization methods with pictures from Google Maps. The suggested technique provides a way to identify the specified regions inside big aerial image, which makes it easier to do a wide range of analysis and applications—especially when it comes to promoting renewable energy sources and urban planning.

IV. METHODS

a. Study Design and Setting

A cross-sectional survey was used as part of the study design to govern the vulnerabilities experienced by rural users and to understand how useful Google Maps is for navigation in remote regions. And through Electronical method, the survey was sent to people having life in rural and urban regions, with an emphasis on getting more feedback from rural consumers [8]. Through a series of well-structured Likert-scale questions, participants were invited to share their opinion.

Participants

Consumers of all ages, genders, occupations, and geographic locations—including both rural and urban location are considered as the study's participants. The survey conducted had 248 participants in all, which gave most important information about how people in rural areas utilize and perceive Google Maps. The demographics of the sample reflected an extensive variety of viewpoints, and allows for a thorough examination of the variables affecting rural navigation experiences.

b. Data collection and analysis

An electronic survey that was made available to the target participants online was used to collect data. Likert-scale questions covering a wide range of topics related to Google Maps usage, difficulties faced by the participants, and satisfaction levels made up the survey. Anonymized responses were collected in order to allow an open communication amongst participants. Appropriate techniques were used in statistical analysis [9] to look into the data that was collected and derive significant findings. To compile participant responds, descriptive statistics were computed, such as numbers and Likert-scale distributions. In addition to this, inferential statistical tests such independent t-tests [10], chi-square tests [11], and analysis of variance (ANOVA) are also used to evaluate the significance of relation between various variables and the perception of Google Maps accuracy in rural locations. The outcome of these statistical analyses provided insights into the effectiveness of Google Maps for rural

navigation and identified regions for improvement.

V. RESULTS

Fig 1 Gender differences in perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas

From the figure 1 we can conclude that there is a substantial difference between how men and women perceive the accuracy of Google Maps in rural areas based on the results of the independent t-test performed on gender and perception of accuracy in rural locales. This results that people's impressions of Google Maps accuracy in rural regions are influenced by their gender.

Fig 2 Occupational differences in perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas

From the figure 2 we may conclude that different vocations do, in fact, have different views of Google Maps' accuracy in rural areas based on the findings of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) performed on occupation and perception of the map's accuracy in rural areas. This recommends that people's impressions about the accuracy of Google Maps in rural areas are influenced by their occupation.

Fig 3 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas based on user experience with challenges

From the figure 3 we can conclude that people who faced the challenges with Google Maps have different perceptions of the app's accuracy than people who don't, based on the output of an independent t-test conducted on the experience of challenges with the app in rural areas and perception of its accuracy in those regions. This implies that people's thoughts of Google Maps' accuracy are influenced by difficulties they have when using it in rural locations.

From the figure 4 we can conclude that different obstacles encountered that leads to different perceptions of Google Maps' accuracy based on the findings of the Chi-square test conducted on the perception of obstacles faced with Google Maps in rural areas and the perception of Google Maps accuracy in rural locations. This recommends that people's opinions about Google Maps' accuracy are influenced by the kinds of challenges they encounter while using it in rural areas.

Fig 4 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas influenced by types of encountered obstacles

From the figure 5 we can conclude that adequate information does, in fact, lead to different perceptions of Google Maps' accuracy compared to inadequate information based on the results of the Chi-square test that is conducted on the perception of adequacy of information provided by Google Maps and perception of Google Maps accuracy in rural locations. This implies that people's choice about how accurate Google Maps

are based on how much information they believe the app to be enough.

From the above figure 6 we can conclude that varying satisfaction levels do, lead to varying perceptions of Google Maps accuracy based on the result of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test performed on the degree of satisfaction with using Google Maps as a navigation tool in rural regions and perception of Google Maps accuracy in rural locations. This implies that people's opinions of Google Maps' accuracy are influenced by how happy when they are using the technology for navigation in rural places.

From the figure 7 we can reach to the conclusion that various views of the accuracy of Google Maps are indeed influenced by feature like awareness based on the findings of the Chi-square test that was really used to examine awareness of features for rural travel and perception of accuracy in rural regions. This implies that the individual opinions of Google Maps accuracy are influenced by their knowledge of the tool rural navigation features.

From the figure 8 we can conclude that different perceptions of Google Maps' accuracy are indeed influenced by how accurately landmarks are depicted. And the conclusion is mainly based on the findings of an independent t-test that was conducted on how accurately people felt the maps depicted landmarks and points of interest, as well as how accurate people thought the google maps were overall in rural location. This implies that people's opinions on how accurate landmarks and other points of interest are on Google Maps affect how accurate they think the app is overall in rural areas.

Fig 5 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas based on adequacy of provided information

Fig 6 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas based on user satisfaction levels

Fig 7 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas based on user awareness of navigation features

Fig 8 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas influenced by depiction of landmarks

From the figure 9 we can conclude that varying levels of satisfaction with additional features do, in fact, lead to varying perceptions of Google Maps' accuracy based on the findings of the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) performed on the satisfaction with extra features offered by Google Maps for rural navigation and perception of Google Maps accuracy in rural locations. This shows that people's opinions of Google Maps' accuracy are influenced by how satisfied they are with the extra features it provides for rural travel.

From the figure 10 we can conclude that the likelihood of recommendation does, in fact, lead to different perceptions of Google Maps' accuracy based on the results of the Chi-square test conducted on the likelihood of recommending Google Maps for navigation in remote areas to someone else and the perception of Google Maps' accuracy in rural locations. This implies that people's opinions of Google Maps' accuracy are influenced by how likely they are to advise it to others for use in remote locations.

Fig 9 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas based on satisfaction with additional features

Fig 10 Perceived Google Maps accuracy in rural areas based on likelihood of recommending it for navigation in remote areas

VI. CONCLUSION

As a result, this study clarifies the difficulties users in rural areas encounter while also highlighting the effectiveness of Google Maps in this regard. It is clear from a thorough study and research that Google Maps is useful for navigating through rural areas, but it also has drawbacks, including inaccurate mapping, a lack of offline capabilities, and a dependence on dependable internet connections.

The findings show that people's perceptions of how accurate Google Maps are in rural areas are influenced by a number of factors, including gender, occupation, experience with challenges, perception of obstacles, adequate information, satisfaction with features, awareness of features, accuracy in depicting landmarks, and likelihood of recommendation.

To address these challenges and improve navigation efficiency and usability in rural areas, it is crucial to consider the insights provided by users. By enhancing mapping accuracy, providing more reliable offline functionality, and offering better support for areas with limited internet connectivity, Google Maps can better meet the navigation needs of rural users. Additionally, increasing awareness of features and improving user satisfaction with extra features can contribute to a more positive perception of Google Maps' accuracy in rural areas. Overall, this research provides valuable insights for enhancing navigation tools in rural areas and facilitating smoother traveling experiences for residents, travellers, and businesses operating in these regions.

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